

ODECO

Towards a sustainable Open Data ECosystem

D1.3

Training Week 1 'Understanding open data as an ecosystem'

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Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
ESR	Early Stage Researcher
M	Milestone
ODECO	Open Data ECOsystem
WP	Work Package

Nr	Partner	Partner short name	Country
Beneficiary			
1	Technische Universiteit Delft	TU Delft	Netherlands
2	Katholieke Universiteit Leuven	KUL	Belgium
3	Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique	CNRS	France
4	Universidad de Zaragoza	UNIZAR	Spain
5	Panepistimio Aigaiou	UAEGEAN	Greece
6	Aalborg Universitet	AAU	Denmark
7	Università degli Studi di Camerino	UNICAM	Italy
8	Farosnet S.A.	FAROSNET S.A.	Greece
Partner organisations			
1	7EDATA	7EDATA	Spain
2	Digitaal Vlaanderen	DV	Belgium
3	City of Copenhagen	COP	Denmark
4	City of Rotterdam	RDAM	Netherlands
5	CoC Playful Minds	CoC	Denmark
6	Derilinx	DERI	Ireland
7	ESRI	ESRI	Netherlands
8	Doctrine	DOCTRINE	France
9	Maggioli S.p.A	MAG	Italy
10	National Centre of Geographic Information	CNIG	Spain
11	Open Knowledge Belgium	OKB	Belgium
12	Spatineo	SPATI	Finland
13	SWECO	SWECO	Netherlands
14	University of Paris Nanterre	UPN	France

1. Introduction

The training week programme in the ODECO project is organised in five training weeks planned to be executed through the entire duration of the project by the various beneficiaries. The issues/subjects covered by the first training week were mutually defined by the beneficiaries of the project regarding the specific needs of the ESRs in their first time period.

1. Training week 1: 'Understanding open data as an ecosystem' (+ Consortium Meeting 1) (AAU M12);
2. Training week 2: 'Towards a user driven open data ecosystem' (+ Consortium Meeting 2) (UNIZAR M18);
3. Training week 3: 'Towards a circular open data ecosystem' (+ Consortium Meeting 3) (UNICAM M24);
4. Training week 4: 'Towards an inclusive open data ecosystem' (+ Consortium Meeting 4) (KULEUVEN M30);
5. Training week 5: 'Towards the open data ecosystem' (+ Consortium Meeting 5) (UAEGEAN M36).

Each training week include the following elements in order to enhance collaboration and communication among the ESRs as well as the whole project team:

- Network events;
- Master classes;
- Professional skills training;
- An outreach activity.

This report is a record of Training week 1 planned and conducted by AAU from Aug. 29th – Sept. 2nd, 2022, at Aalborg University in Copenhagen Denmark.

1.1. Training week programme objective, learning objectives and contents

The overall objective of Training Week 1 was to get ESRs acquainted with sectoral and disciplinary perspective and practices on open data (research). The programme thus aimed to stimulate collaboration both between the ESRs, but also between ESRs and external partners such as organisations and industry with an open data focus.

The objectives of the week were also to support the ESRs in gaining an interdisciplinary perspective through training with focus on interdisciplinary learning and research concepts, approaches/ methods, and activities of the open data ecosystem taught by project beneficiaries. The third objective was to provide professional skills training in research/ education ethics and professional integrity, team working, group dynamics and in organising (public) events. Finally, the objective was to engage ESRs in an outreach event with round table discussion with relevant stakeholders.

The project beneficiaries responsible for training sessions participated in the preparation and implementation of the training programme.

1.2. Setup of the programme

Training week was planned a five full day programme with social events on all days with the following themes for the independent days:

Table 1: Overview of the planned activities in training week 1

Day	Activity
Day 1	ODECO Network Day ESR progress presentations to the ODECO network
Day 2	Open data in practice - academic, NGO, government and business perspectives and lessons learned (with input and support from partner organisations and organisations outside the ODECO project)
Day 3	Masterclass: Interdisciplinary learning and research concepts, approaches/ methods, and activities of the open data ecosystem (UPN, AAU & UNICAM)
Day 4	Professional Skills Training: IPR in research/ education (CNRS); ethics and professional integrity (UPN); Team working, group dynamics, organising (public) events (UAEGEAN)
Day 5	Outreach event (due to change in partner consortium this day was cancelled)

Due to some last-minute changes in the partner consortium (the partner UPN and lectures on day 4 left the ODECO project few days before the start of training week 1), the programme was rescheduled and the program on day five was cancelled.

The final rescheduled programme therefore was a four-day programme of:

1. ESRs presentations;
2. Partner presentations;
3. Masterclasses;
4. Professional skill training.

Table 2: Final programme for training week 1, brief version

Day	Activity
Day 1: Aug. 29 th	ODECO Network Day: 15 minutes presentations from each ESR + discussions
Day 2: Aug. 30 th	Open data in practice: academic, NGO, government and business perspectives and lessons learned (with input and support from all partner organisations), 15 minutes presentations, 15 minute discussion after each presentation
Day 3: Aug. 31 st	Interdisciplinary learning and research concepts, approaches/ methods, and activities of the open data ecosystem: Beneficiary lectures and activities, Lectures: AAU, CNRS & UNICAM
Day 4: Sept. 1 st	Professional skills training: Beneficiary lectures and activities IPR in research/ education (CNRS); ethics and professional integrity; Team working, group dynamics, organising (public) events (UAEGEAN). Evaluation of training week

The detailed program for the various days will be presented in the following sections.

Invitations for Training Week 1 was sent out three months before the event to ESRs and beneficiaries.

1.3. Credits

It was agreed to issue a certificate of achievement for the training week at AAU for 50 hours workload as each country has different standards for what workloads reflect ECTS (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System). The certificate was sent to all ESRs after the training week.

1.4. Supervisors attending the training week

The following supervisors were present during the training week either physical at the meetings at AAU I Copenhagen or online on a zoom link:

Table 3: Supervisors present at the training week

Supervisors
Bastiaan van Loenen (TUDELFT)
Rikke Magnussen (AAU)
Francisco Javier López Pellicer and Javier Nogueras (UNIZAR)
Melanie Dulong de Rosnay (CNRS, online participation)
Charalabidis Yannis (UAEGEAN, online participation)
Andrea Polini (UNICAM)

1.5. Social activities

To strengthen team building and networking between ESRs social activities had been planned for all evenings. The social activities both included dinners at community houses in Copenhagen, boat trips and social guide tour arranged by a non-profit company who arrange guide tours with homeless people.

Table 4: Social activities of training week 1

Date	Social activity
Day 1: Aug. 29 th	ESR'S shared dinner in Folkehuset Absalon (community house dinner)
Day 2: Aug. 30 th	Walk guided tour with Gadens Stemmer and Fishtank visit. Gadens Stemmer (Voices of the Street) is a grassroots initiative (Fish tank is a ODECO partnership organisation)
Day 3: Aug. 31 st	Boat trip GoBoat Copenhagen
Day 4: Sept. 1 st	Dinner Cofoco restaurant (all beneficiaries and ESRs)

The social activities were an important element in the training week and was evaluated very well by all participants. It was evaluated that the positive dynamics and team building between ESRs during the week was a direct consequence of the extensive program of social activities and highly positive for the ODECO training goals.

2. Day 1 – Introduction and ESR presentations

2.1. Objectives, activities, assignments, and program

Day 1 was planned as the ODECO Network Day. The full day 1 program consisted of fourteen 15 min. progress presentations from all ESRs to the ODECO network. After presentations there were a 45 min. session planned where supervisors discussed projects with groups of ESRs. The social event in the evening program was a planned dinner at a community house in Copenhagen. The detailed day program is described in Table 5.

Table 5: Program Day 1

Date	Day Activity	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location
Aug. 29th	Day 1: ODECO Network Day Format: 15 minutes each ESR + discussions	Intro	9.30		AAU
		ESR progress presentations to the ODECO network <	9.40	ESR 15	A. C. Meyers Vænge 15, 2450 Copenhagen. Seminar room 2.1.042 at Globegangen Format: Hybrid online/offline (Please note that it is NOT the same seminar room at AAU on Monday and Tuesday. Monday is 2.1.042. Booked from 8.15-16.15.)
			9.55	ESR 14	
			10.10	ESR 13	
			10.25	ESR 12	
			10.40	Q&A ESRs	
			10.45	Break	
			11.00	ESR 11	
			11.15	ESR 10	
			11.30	ESR 9	
			11.45	ESR 8	
			12.00	Q&A ESRs	
			12.10	Lunch	
			13.00	ESR 7	
			13.15	ESR 6	
			13.30	ESR 5	
			13.45	Q&A ESRs	
			13.55	Break	
			14.10	ESR 3	
			14.25	ESR 2	
		14.40	ESR 1		
		14.55	Q&A ESRs		
			Speed dating	15.00 - 16.00	Beneficiaries and partners move around to ESRs tables to discuss talks and projects. They change seats every 10 min. to ensure that supervisors meet multiple ESRs.
		16.00 End of day: break before social event in the evening			

Date	Day Activity	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location
		SOCIAL EVENT. ESR'S shared dinner in Folkehuset Absalon (Book with final number of participants)	17.45 - 19.30		

The assignment for Day 1 was for ESRs to prepare presentations. There was no mandatory literature for the preparation of the day.

2.2. Evaluation of day 1

Overall, the day was evaluated to be well managed with interesting presentations from all ESRs. There were however suggestions to possible changes for future training weeks. Overall, there were comments that there should be more supervisors present either physically or online which would create more time for feedback. Four beneficiaries/supervisors attended day 1 physically at the AAU campus in Copenhagen: Bastiaan van Loenen (TUDELFT), Rikke Magnussen (AAU) and Francisco Javier López Pellicer and Javier Nogueras (UNIZAR).

There were also discussions if the presentations should be split into tracks dependent on domains. This was discussed as there were different opinions on if all participants should listen to all presentations or they should be split into tracks. Finally, it was agreed that the format should be 10 min. presentations for all ESRs to listen to all tracks and that supervision should then be split into tracks dependent on the domain where ERSs within the related fields were supervised together. It was also agreed that Miro boards should be provided for collecting comments during talks, and that the topic of the week should be concluded on by the end of the week.

3. Day 2 – Presentations from partner organisations and organisations outside ODECO working with open data

3.1. Objectives, activities, assignments, and program

The overall objective of Day 2 was for the ESRs; to get acquainted with sectoral and disciplinary perspective and practices on open data (research). The program consisted of eight 15 min. talks followed by 15 minutes of discussion between representatives from organisations, ESRs and beneficiaries. The visiting speakers represented academic, NGO, government and business perspectives and had been asked to talk about lessons learned in their respective context.

The speakers represented both Danish and European private or governmental organisations with focus on open data and big data in general. The visiting organisations were both highly motivated by the detailed discussions of open data perspectives, but also highly interested in the ESR perspectives and results, as well as future career development as several of the organisations were interested in employing profiles with open data expertise. It was a full day program and the ESRs had been asked to list questions for the speakers and to do a short presentation of their Ph.D. topic before posing a question. This was to allow Ph.D.'s to be introduced to organisations, which would be potential interesting collaboration partners.

The programme thus aimed to stimulate collaboration between ESRs and external partners such as organisations and industry with an open data focus. The visiting organisations both participated online and physically at AAU in Copenhagen, and the interactive programme created highly interesting discussions both between ESRs and partner organisations, and between partner organisations that created networking meetings both during and after the training week.

Table 6: Program Day 2

Date	Day Activity	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location
Tuesday Aug. 30th	Day 2 Format: 15 minutes each presentation + 15 discussion Open data in practice: academic, NGO, government and business perspectives and lessons learned (with input and support from all partner organizations)	Intro to Open data in practice	9.00		AAU A. C. Meyers Vænge 15, 2450 Copenhagen. Seminar room 2.1.043 at Globegangen
		Danish Agency for Data Supply	9:30	Peter Knudsen will share his experience as chief consultant in the Danish Agency for Data Supply	
		Danish Agency for Digitisation	10:00	Martin Skovbjerg will share insights as a consultant in the Danish Agency for Digitisation.	
		Break	10.30		
		Presentation CoC Playful Minds	10.45	Karin Møller Villumsen will share insights from Playful Minds	
		Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission	11:15	Anders Friis-Christensen, Scientific officer (team leader) will share his experience with Open Data initiatives both at JRC and at the Commission.	
		Lunch			11.45

Date	Day Activity	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location	
		Spatineo, Belgium	12:45	Jaana Mäkelä director of business development in Spatineo quality assurance expert for spatial web services with strong INSPIRE and OGC expertise. *Online participation		
		Sweco	13.15	Mr. Henri Veldhuis, business unit manager at SWECO. Sweco Europe is a leading engineering and architecture consultancy that plans and designs the sustainable communities and cities of the future. *Online participation		
		Break	13.45			
		Agency for Data Supply and Efficiency	14.00	Ulla Kronborg Mazzoli is Chief Advisor for the Danish Agency for Data Supply and Infrastructure, where she works with digital government, data infrastructure, data-driven innovation, and value creation, recently in the context of data ecosystems. She is the national INSPIRE Contact Point and Danish representative in several EU expert groups. Ulla holds a Master of Science in Geography and a diploma degree in Leadership and Management. She is the chair of the Danish Association for Geographic Information's International Committee.		
		City of Rotterdam	14.30 - 15	Jochem Cooman, Innovation officer at the City of Rotterdam will share the experience with Open Data from the perspective of the municipality of Rotterdam. *Online participation		
		15.00: Closure				
		ODECO Board Meeting	15.30 - 17.30	Supervisory board meeting		
		SOCIAL EVENT. Walking tour with Gadens Stemmer	17.30 - 20.00	Walk guided tour with Gadens Stemmer * and Fishtank visit. Gadens Stemmer (Voices of the Street) is a grassroots initiative hosted in ODECO's partner organization Fishtank Social Hub. They offer city walks focused on the guide's personal story from a life at	Meeting point in Jarmers Plats	

Date	Day Activity	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location
				the edge of society. The project focuses on providing to all people an opportunity to unfold positively in interaction with society.	

The assignment for Day 1 was for ESRs to prepare questions for partner presentations. There was no mandatory literature for the preparation of the day.

3.2. Evaluation of Day 2

The partner collaboration day was overall very well received by the ESRs. They overall expressed that the detailed presentations of professional perspectives from outside partners was highly interesting and inspiring and that it was a great opportunity to meet partners to develop possible collaboration. New secondments possibilities may be a result of the networking activities on day 2. This should further be discussed and verified at future supervisor board meetings.

At the evaluation it was discussed whether there in future training weeks should be tracks with partner talks where theme of tracks should correspond with Ph.D. themes. There was however, no consensus on this as other ESRs saw partner presentations as cross-disciplinary including several themes and approaches. There were suggestions that asking for a meeting should be arranged after the official program or that partner organisations receive short presentation videos of ESRs to be able to direct their talks to the ESRs topics.

Moreover, there were further comments on that; not all ESR topics were covered in the invitation of speakers e.g., that there were no NGO representatives. There should be focus on this in the planning of future training weeks. Another comment addressed that most talks were about systems but not ecosystems or complex systems involving users and that the social science or economics perspectives were not addressed. It was suggested that there should be a physical board in the conference room where topics within the overall topic – open data ecosystems – could be listed and addressed by the end of the week.

4. Day 3 – Interdisciplinary learning and research concepts, approaches/ methods

4.1. Objectives and program

The main objective of Day 3 in Training Week 1 was to support the ESRs in gaining an interdisciplinary perspective through training with focus on interdisciplinary learning and research concepts, approaches/methods, and activities of the open data ecosystem taught by project beneficiaries. The lectures focused on beneficiaries' subjects to inspire ESRs with interdisciplinary learning and research concepts. Due to the last-minute changes in the training week schedule, an online lecture on professional training (copyright law) by CNRS was rescheduled from Day 4 to Day 3.

Table 7: Program Day 3

Date	Day Activity	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location
Aug. 31st	Day 3: Interdisciplinary learning and research concepts, approaches/ methods, and activities of the open data ecosystem (AAU, CNRS & UNICAM)	Intro	9.00		Scandic Sluseholmen, Molestien 11, 2450 Copenhagen
		Lecture beneficiary AAU	9:15	<u>Lecture: Open data in education</u> 1. Theoretical and methodological background in the learning sciences 2. AAU research in open data in education. 3. Discuss related areas such as citizen science, open source - differences and similarities	
		Break	10:15		
		Activity and ESR presentations beneficiary AAU	10.25	<u>Activity:</u> <u>Identify educational needs and designs</u> 1. Identify actors and possible lack of skills or competencies in your cases 2. Discuss possibilities for education/learning between actors 3. Develop suggestions for an educational approach/design in one of your cases. Final discussion of ideas in plenum LITERATURE: Saddiqa et al. 2021 https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360131521001718	
		Break	11.25		
		Activity and ESR presentations beneficiary CNRS (online/hybrid) (guest lecture: Andrés Guadamuz, Sussex Law School)	11.35	<u>Lecture and Q&A: Laws applicable to data (CNRS)</u> 1. Copyright law 2. Sui generis rights 3. Other rights: data protection	
	Lunch		12.35		

Date	Day	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location
		Activity and ESR presentations beneficiary CNRS (online/hybrid) (guest seminar: Andrés Guadamuz, Sussex Law School)	13.15	<u>Lecture and Q&A part II: Laws applicable to data (CNRS)</u> 1. Copyright law 2. Sui generis rights 3. Other rights: data protection	
		Break	14.15		
		Lecture beneficiary UNICAM	14.25	<u>Lecture: Research Methodology</u> 1. What is research? 2. Research Questions 3. Research Strategies 4. Literature Review 5. Thesis Statement	
		Break	15.25		
		Activity and ESR presentations beneficiary UNICAM	15.35	<u>Activity:</u> ESRs are divided in 5 groups. ESRs further reflect on their research activity and formulate/refine the research questions they intend to answer during their PhD to permit the discussion with their group colleagues. The different research strategies are considered in relation to their research objectives.	
		Closure	16.35		
		SOCIAL EVENT. Boat trip GoBoat Copenhagen	18-21.00	Book with final number of participants *Check weather	

4.2. Lectures and activities

Three different lectures and types of activities were planned for Day 4:

1. Open data in education (AAU)
2. Laws applicable to data (CNRS, professional training lecture moved from Day 4)
3. Research Methodology (UNICAM)

The lectures and activities will be described below

Open data in education

In this lecture, ESRs were introduced to approaches to understanding education and learning in open data ecosystems. The lecture was conducted physically by beneficiary AAU associate professor Rikke

Magnussen. Various theories for learning in communities, individual cognitive learning, and theories for understanding users' motivation was introduced. The focus in this lecture was to inspire ERSs to see open data actors as learners and reflect on how to address learning needs of actors in the various systems that ERSs studies.

The lecture was followed by an activity where the ERSs were split into groups to discuss and come up with suggestions to possible learning activities in their various cases. The groups had to analyse the following elements of designing a learning activity: a. learners – identities, previous experiences etc., b. learning environment – tools, resources etc., c. learning outcomes – new knowledge, new possibilities for action etc., others – support, platforms etc. After the activity results were discussed in plenum.

Mandatory reading:

Saddiqa et al. 2021

<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0360131521001718>

Laws applicable to data (CNRS, professional training lecture moved from Day 4)

The lecture on laws applicable to data belonged to the Day 4 program with focus on professional training but was - because of the last minute changes in the program – moved to Day 3. The lecture and activity were conducted online by beneficiary CNRS by guest lecturer: Andrés Guadamuz from Sussex Law School. The lecture consisted of three topics:

1. Copyright law
2. Sui generis rights
3. Other rights: data protection

The session consisted of a lecture and a discussion between the guest lecturer and the ERSs at the end of the session. There was no mandatory reading for this session.

Research methodology

The training session on research methodology consisted of a lecture and an activity conducted physically by associate professor Andrea Polini from beneficiary UNICAM. The lecture on research methodology addressed the following topics:

1. What is research?
2. Research Questions
3. Research Strategies
4. Literature Review
5. Thesis Statement

After the lecture, an activity was conducted where ERSs were divided into groups to further reflect on their research activities and formulate/refine the research questions that they intended to answer during their PhD. The task in the groups was also to consider different research strategies in relation to the various research objectives in the Ph.D.'s. There was no mandatory reading for this session.

4.3 Evaluation of Day

Overall, the lectures and activities were very well received by ERSs. ERSs both mentioned that it was inspiring to apply the various cross-disciplinary approaches to their studies, and that the cross-disciplinary discussions and activities also connected them to other ERSs perspectives, which created nice discussions. Overall, it was expressed that lectures on learning theories and research methods were academic activities that inspired the PhD topics. Some of the sessions on day 1 and 2 stayed very close to the subject OD. It was nice also to have days with theoretical perspectives on topics – such as lectures on learning theories and research methodology – as a supplement to the more specific OD sessions on the first days in the training week. It was expressed that it was important to keep cross-disciplinary lectures with activities in future training weeks.

There were comments to the technical standard of the online lectures. The technical quality should be secured for online lectures in future training weeks.

5. Day 4 – Professional skills training

5.1. Objectives, program, lectures, and activities

The objective of Day 4 was to provide professional skills training in research/ education ethics, professional integrity, team working, group dynamics and in organizing (public) events. The day included two training sessions:

1. Team working, group dynamics, organizing (public) events (UAEGEAN)
2. IPR in research/ education, ethics, and professional integrity (online, CNRS)

The two sessions were followed by a discussion between beneficiaries and ESRs about the presented perspectives relation to ESRs Ph.D. contexts.

Table 8: Program Day 4

Date	Day Activity	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location
Sep. 1st	Day 4: Professional skills training IPR in research/ education (CNRS); ethics and professional integrity ; Team working, group dynamics, organizing (public) events (UAEGEAN)	Intro	9.00		Scandic Sluseholmen , Molestien 11, 2450 Copenhagen
		Lecture Yannis Charalabidis, UAEGEAN	9.15	From the idea to pitch-deck: Strategy and tactics for a successful conception, description and presentation of innovation	
		Break	10.15		
		Activity Yannis Charalabidis, UAEGEAN	10 25	Discussion on specific ESRs cases about their projects	
		Break	11.25		
		Lecture beneficiary CNRS (online/hybrid) Melanie Dulong de Rosnay, CNRS	11.35	<p><u>Lecture: Open licensing and data commons</u></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Open licensing 2. Principles and recommendations 3. Data commons <p><u>References</u> (for after the class)</p> <p>Fair principles: https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/</p> <p>Anouk Ruhaak, Greg Bloom, Angie Raymond, Willa Tavernier, Divya Siddarth, Gary Motz and Melanie Dulong de Rosnay, 2021, A Practical Framework for Applying Ostrom’s Principles to Data Commons Governance https://foundation.mozilla.org/en/blog/a-practical-framework-for-applying-ostroms-principles-to-data-commons-governance/</p> <p>Mélanie Dulong de Rosnay, Felix Stalder, 2020, "Digital Commons", <i>Internet Policy Review</i>, 9(4). ISSN: 2197-6775. DOI: 10.14763/2020.4.1530.</p>	
		Lunch	12.35		

Date	Day Activity	Detailed Activity	Time	Responsible	Location
		Activity and ESR presentations beneficiary CNRS (online/hybrid) Melanie Dulong de Rosnay, CNRS	13.15	<p><u>Lecture: Data ethics, Professional and scientific integrity</u> Data ethics Research ethics Research integrity Professional integrity</p> <p><u>Activity:</u> Discuss cases of problems of professional integrity and possible remedies in various countries, situations (PhD student, PhD advisor, director of PhD programme, etc.), social and professional norms in research communities: who to contact when you face a problem: legal enforcement, ethics committees, professional associations</p> <p><u>Literature</u> (for after the class) What is data ethics? Luciano Floridi and Mariarosaria Taddeo Published:28 December 2016 https://doi.org/10.1098/rsta.2016.0360</p>	
		Break	14.15		
		Danitsja	14:30	Introduction to platform	
		Evaluation: evaluation of the independent days in the training week	15.00	Present: Francisco Javier López Pellicer, Javier Noguerras, Rikke Magnussen and Yannis Charalabidis	
		Closure	16.00		
		SOCIAL EVENT. Dinner Cofoco restaurant (all beneficiaries and ESRs)	18.00 - 20.00		

Session 1: Teamwork, group dynamics, organizing (public) events (UAEGEAN)

The focus of the lecture in this professional training session was to professionally train ESRs in developing their projects from the idea to pitch-deck. Focus was on how to develop strategy and tactics for a successful conception, description and presentation of innovation. The lecture was followed by a discussion on the specific ESRs cases and projects. There were no mandatory reading for this session.

Session 2: IPR in research/ education, ethics, and professional integrity (online, CNRS)

This session was an online lecture followed by a discussion about the presented perspectives. The lecture addressed three topics: a. Open licensing, b. Principles and recommendations, c. Data commons. The lecture was followed by a discussion on the specific ESRs cases and projects.

There was no mandatory reading before class, but several reference was listed for future reading:

- Fair principles: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>
- Anouk Ruhaak, Greg Bloom, Angie Raymond, Willa Tavernier, Divya Siddarth, Gary Motz and Melanie Dulong de Rosnay, 2021, A Practical Framework for Applying Ostrom's Principles to Data Commons Governance
- <https://foundation.mozilla.org/en/blog/a-practical-framework-for-applying-ostroms-principles-to-data-commons-governance/>
- Mélanie Dulong de Rosnay, Felix Stalder, 2020, "Digital Commons", Internet Policy Review, 9(4). ISSN: 2197-6775. DOI: 10.14763/2020.4.1530.

5.2 Evaluation of day 4 and training week 1 in general

The evaluation comments for day 4 were similar to the comments from day 3. Overall, the students were happy about the program, but preferred physical lectures to online.

The comments to the overall week were very appreciative. ESRs expressed that the AAU team had created a well-structured and interesting training week.

There were a few comments to future training weeks:

- There should be a wrap up by the end of the week in regard to the overall topic of the week (training week 1: open data ecosystems)
- The full day program in training week was exhausting. It was suggested to keep the 5 days program but either make the days lighter – longer breaks, shift of setting etc. – or do something out of program on day 3.
- Participants should remember to tweet about the week
- Online lectures should be avoided if possible or made shorter.

6. Summary & Conclusions

Training week 1 was developed and implemented as a five-day course with the following objectives:

1. To get ESRs acquainted with sectoral and disciplinary perspective and practices on open data (research)
2. To stimulate collaboration both between the ESRs and external partners such as organisations and industry with an open data focus.
3. To support the ESRs in gaining an interdisciplinary perspective
4. To provide professional skills training in research/ education ethics and professional integrity, team working, group dynamics and in organizing (public) events.

The training week ran from August 29th to September 2nd and include the following days and activities:

- DAY 1 ODECO Network Day ESR progress presentations to the ODECO network
- DAY 2 Open data in practice - academic, NGO, government and business perspectives and lessons learned (with input and support from partner organisations and organisations outside the ODECO project)
- DAY 3 Masterclass: Interdisciplinary learning and research concepts, approaches/ methods, and activities of the open data ecosystem (UPN, AAU & UNICAM)
- DAY 4 Professional Skills Training: IPR in research/ education (CNRS); ethics and professional integrity (UPN); Team working, group dynamics, organising (public) events (UAEGEAN)
- DAY 5 Outreach event (due to change in partner consortium this day was cancelled)

The training week was overall evaluated positively by ESRs and beneficiaries with minor comments to length of days, content and form.

6.1. Points for the next Training Week

Analysing the evaluation results of each day, the following tips should be taken into account during the design of the next training week:

1. ESR presentations should be shorter (10 min) allowing for longer feedback sessions from supervisors in tracks dependent on topic
2. The partner organisation-networking day should be included in the following training weeks as well. When inviting partner organisations, it should be ensured that there are representatives from the different contexts and fields of the ESRs Ph.D. work e.g., NGOs, private organisations and government or local government partners
3. The cross-disciplinary teaching sessions and the professional training were a success and should be part of future training weeks too. It is good to combine with sessions tightly related to the open data field with sessions with a more theoretical approach
4. A stable web connection should be ensured for online attendance
5. The week should still be a 5-day week but with either longer breaks, shorter days or a break or shift in scenery in the middle of the week
6. The social evening program was a success and should be kept strengthening team building and networking between ESRs